

A Mechanistic Study on 3-Arylazopentane-2,4-diones and some of its Derivatives at a Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode

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Manuscript received 5 August 1996, revised 4 March 1997, accepted 21 August 1997

The polarographic reduction of 3-arylazopentane-2,4-diones has been investigated in 40% ethanolic B.R. buffer series (pH 2.6–11.7) at mercury cathode. In all pH values four electrons are involved in the reduction cleavage of N=N center followed by reduction of one of the carbonyl groups present in the examined compounds by two electrons confirmed by controlled potential electrolysis. However, the voltammograms of these compounds display a single irreversible cathodic peak over the entire pH range. The different kinetic parameters of the electron transfer process are evaluated where possible using convolution, deconvolution analysis of the recorded cyclic voltammetric data often combined with digital simulation studies.

Arylazocarbonyl compounds have been found to play an important role in the field of pharmaceutical chemistry as they possess interesting anticoplastic or antiadiabetic activity^{1,2} and in organic compounds as powerful chelating agents².

The principal goal of the present work is to consider the voltammetric reduction pathway of 3-arylazopentane-2,4-diones (**1a-e**). The electroactive centers present in these compounds are the C=O and N=N groups. Compounds containing these two groups separately have been investigated³, but few studies were made on compounds which contain both of them.

Results and Discussion

DC polarography: The electroreduction of the 3-arylazopentane-2,4-diones (**1a-e**) has been studied in Britton-Robinson buffer solution of pH 2.6–11.7 containing 40% ethanol.

The polarographic results of the parent compound is shown in Fig. 1. The polarographic response of all compounds at a dropping mercury electrode is similar, since all are reduced through a first four-electron irreversible cathodic wave over the entire pH range which corresponds to cleavage of the azo group into the amine stage. A second polarographic reduction two-electron wave appears

in acidic medium, neutral and slightly alkaline solutions corresponding to the reduction of at least one of the carbonyl groups present in the molecule. The gradual decrease of the limiting currents of the second cathodic wave in alkaline media may be ascribed to the hydration of one of the carbonyl groups⁴ present in the depolarizer molecule until the wave disappears at pH > 10.5.

Fig. 1. Polarogram for the reduction of **1a** at a mercury drop electrode; concn. = 2.5×10^{-4} M, temp. = 20°.

The presence of adsorption and some chemical contributions affecting the electron transfer process of the depolarizers under consideration, were confirmed from the values of the slope (0.39–0.71) of the plots of $\log i_l$ as a function of $\log h$ (i_l = limiting current and h = mercury height) at different pH values.

Logarithmic analysis of the polarographic waves for

all compounds under consideration shows the slowness of the electron transfer process, as gradient of logarithmic plots shifts from the predicted theoretical value of 59 mV per pH unit for reversible electron transfer⁵. The higher the pH of the solution, the slower is the electron transfer. Values of symmetry coefficients at varying pH values in the case of a non-Nerstian system have been evaluated by logarithmic analysis of polarographic waves. The most probable values of symmetry coefficients along the entire pH range for the first and second waves indicate that the rate-determining step of the electrode process may involve two electrons (Table 2).

The polarographic half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) of the depolarizer under consideration shifted to more negative values with increasing pH of the medium. This indicates the involvement of protons in the rate-determining step and the proton transfer probably precedes the electron transfer process.

Controlled potential electrolysis : The number of electrons consumed in the electroreduction of the first and the second polarographic wave is confirmed by controlled potential electrolysis experiments (Table 1). Knowing the number of electrons transferred in the polarographic response at different pH, provides a route for calculating the diffusion coefficients of the electroactive reactant species using Ilkovic equation⁶.

Cyclic voltammetry and digital simulation : The cyclic voltammetric data of the 3-arylazopentane-2,4-diones at a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) in acidic, neutral and alkaline solutions containing 40% ethanol at 20° (concentration, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$), were analysed using the Condecon system, to study the nature of electron trans-

TABLE 2—VALUES OF α AND αn_a FOR $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ SOLUTION OF COMPOUNDS 1 IN AQUEOUS BUFFER SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS pH VALUES CONTAINING 40% ETHANOL AT 20°*

Compd. pH	S mV	αn_a	α	
			$n_a = 1$	$n_a = 2$
1a				
3.60	83.13	0.71	0.71	0.36
5.50 (a)	74.79	0.79	0.79	0.39
(b)	60.35	0.98	0.98	0.49
11.70	60.35	0.98	0.98	0.49
1b				
3.65	101.78	0.58	0.58	0.29
7.80 (a)	81.83	0.72	0.72	0.36
(b)	109.81	0.54	0.54	0.27
11.60	51.73	1.14	1.14	0.57
1c				
3.75	60.31	0.98	0.98	0.49
5.65 (a)	47.89	1.23	1.23	0.62
(b)	79.43	0.74	0.74	0.37
10.65	49.31	1.20	1.20	0.60

*S = 0.059/ αn_a ; (a) = first wave; (b) = second wave.

fer process and to evaluate chemical and electrochemical parameters.

From the breadth ($E_p - E_{p/2}$) of the cyclic voltammetric response for all the compounds, the values of symmetry coefficients (Table 3) were calculated using equation (1) for irreversible system⁷,

$$E_p - E_{p/2} = \frac{0.048}{\alpha n_a} V \text{ at } 25^\circ \quad (1)$$

The peak widths ($E_p - E_{p/2}$) at different scan rates are greater than those obtained in the case of the fast electron transfer system ($54.9/n V$ at 20°)⁷.

The heterogeneous rate constant (k_s) was determined from the shift of E_p with $\log v$ via equation (2)⁸,

$$E_p = E^0 - \frac{RT}{\alpha n_a F} \left(0.78 - \frac{2.3}{2} \log \frac{\alpha n_a F D}{k_s^2} \right) - \frac{2.3RT}{2\alpha n_a F} \log v \quad (2)$$

The diffusion coefficient (D) was calculated from the limiting convoluted current (I_{lim}). α , D and k_s were tested and verified from superposition of digital simulated wave and experimental data using Condecon EG & G software. It seems that the higher the pH value, the lower is the value of k_s . This probably indicates that there is a certain degree of sluggishness in the rate of electron transfer. Digital simulation has been proven to be a useful approach to elucidate electrochemical reaction mechanism. The effectiveness of the digital simulation procedure lies in its comparability of the experimental to the theoretical cyclic voltammograms. The theoretical cyclic

TABLE 1—CONTROLLED POTENTIAL ELECTROLYSIS DATA FOR COMPOUNDS 1 AT 20°

Compd. pH	Potential	W (g) $\times 10^{-4}$	Q C	n
1a				
2.65	-0.80	1.28	0.23	3.8
6.70	-1.00	1.28	0.24	4.0
	-1.50	1.28	0.36	5.9
11.60	-1.75	1.28	0.25	4.0
1b				
2.70	-0.70	1.36	0.23	3.8
6.85	-1.05	1.36	0.25	4.1
	-1.45	1.36	0.36	6.0
11.55	-1.20	1.36	0.23	3.8
1d				
2.65	-0.70	1.49	0.24	3.9
6.90	-1.00	1.49	0.25	4.2
	-1.50	1.49	0.35	5.8
11.60	-1.15	1.49	0.24	3.9

TABLE 3—ELECTROCHEMICAL PARAMETERS EXTRACTED FROM CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY, CHRONOPOTENTIOMETRY AND CHRONOCOULOMETRY FOR COMPOUNDS 1 AT HMDE AND AT 20°*

Compd.	pH	mV/s	k_s m/s	I_{lim} $\times 10^6$ A/s ^{1/2}	D $\times 10^9$ m ² /s	α	$E_{1/2}$ V
1a	2.05	200	4.81×10^{-8} (a)	3.24 (a)	1.32 (a)	0.54 (a)	0.31 (b)
			4.80×10^{-8} (b)		1.30 (b)		
	11.2	100	9.82×10^{-12} (a)	3.34 (a)	1.36 (c)	0.50 (a)	0.40 (b)
			9.80×10^{-12} (b)		1.39 (d)		
1c	7.0	100	1.82×10^{-9} (a)	3.63 (a)	1.25 (a)	0.47 (a)	0.31 (b)
			3.30×10^{-9} (b)		1.26 (b)		
	10.7	100	4.82×10^{-12} (a)	3.52 (a)	1.21 (c)	0.52 (a)	0.36 (b)
			4.80×10^{-12} (b)		1.25 (d)		
1d	4.5	100	1.05×10^{-8} (a)	3.65 (a)	1.42 (a)	0.44 (a)	0.23 (b)
			1.05×10^{-8} (b)		1.42 (b)		
	10.4	200	4.63×10^{-12} (a)	3.38 (a)	1.45 (c)	0.49 (a)	0.32 (b)
			4.60×10^{-12} (b)		1.49 (d)		
					1.65 (a)		
					1.65 (b)		
					1.69 (c)		
					1.64 (d)		
					1.75 (a)		
					1.74 (b)		
					1.72 (c)		
					1.78 (d)		
					1.86 (a)		
					1.85 (b)		
					1.92 (c)		
					1.96 (d)		

*(a) = Cyclic voltammetry; (b) = digital simulation; (c) = chronopotentiometry; (d) = chromocoulometry.

voltammogram could be successfully simulated on the computer using the same experimental parameters.

Digital simulation for CV of this system, assuming different values for the $E_{1/2}$ (half-wave potential), with the knowledge of k_s for electron transfer process and symmetry coefficient (α) was carried out until an acceptable fit was obtained for the electrochemical data. These assumed $E_{1/2}$ values (Table 3) were used to simulate the theoretical CV response. The simulated curves which represent the totally irreversible current-potential curve are in good agreement with the background subtracted experimental curve. This agreement supports the assumption that the reaction is controlled by a sluggish charge transfer reaction rate although it is accompanied by a follow-up chemical reaction, EC_{irrev} ⁸. Fig. 2 shows the best fit obtained between the experimental CV scans (solid lines) and computer-simulated voltammograms (dotted lines) for the azocarbonyl compounds at a hanging mercury drop electrode. The adsorption nature of the compounds accounts for some deviations in the shape of experimental voltammograms from the simulated CV⁹.

The peak currents for all compounds under examina-

Fig. 2. Voltammograms for the first reduction wave of **1a** at a HMDE : (—) experimental, (-----) theoretical; sweep rate = 100 mV s⁻¹, pH = 2.1, concn. = 1×10^{-4} M, temp. = 20°.

tion increased as sweep rates were increased as indicated from the linear plots of peak current (i_p) versus the square-root of sweep rate ($v^{1/2}$) with little deviation from the origin. This confirmed that the electron transfer process is accompanied by some adsorption and chemical con-

tributions⁹, which are in a good agreement with the data previously obtained from DC polarography.

Convolution and deconvolution treatments of the electrochemical currents: The analysis of cyclic voltammetric data is based upon the current and potential values of a few specific points. It is much more preferable to use as many data as possible for an effective analysis and convolution-deconvolution method has been proposed which for simple mechanisms allows all data to be assessed. For simple electron transfer, the I_1 convoluted current¹⁰ at

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{\pi^{1/2}} \int_0^t \frac{i(u)}{(t-u)^{1/2}} du \quad (3)$$

All data captured for compounds under investigation show the same response toward quantitative analysis using convolution and deconvolution procedures¹¹. It was observed that the I_1 convolution does not return exactly to its initial (zero) value on cyclic sweeping (Fig. 3), indicating that there is some chemical loss in the electro-reduction process regardless of the scan rate. This indicates that the electroreduction behavior of the electroactive reactant species under consideration is due to slow electron transfer coupled with a fast chemical reaction⁸.

Fig. 3. Convoluted current for the first reduction wave of 1a at a sweep rate of 100 mV s^{-1} , $\text{pH} = 2.1$, $\text{concn.} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $\text{temp.} = 20^\circ$.

Varying the sweep rate caused no change in the plateau height of the I_1 convoluted current (Fig. 3). This confirms that there are no regenerative processes occurring in the experimental time-scale. The plateau height of the I_1 convoluted currents at varying sweep rates from 20 to 500 mV/s are constant and this allows the evaluation of diffusion coefficients for all electroactive reactant species under consideration. Under diffusion controlled conditions, well past the wave, the concentration

of the electroactive species at the electrode surface is equal to zero ($C_{(0,t)} = 0$)¹², so the maximum convoluted current¹³ obtained can be written as

$$I_{\text{lim}} = nFaD^{1/2}C^* \quad (4)$$

and

$$D^{1/2} = I_{\text{lim}}/nFaC^* \quad (5)$$

where a is the electrode area, n the number of electrons transferred and C the concentration of the electroactive species. This expression is valid no matter what form of the potential disturbance used to drive the concentration of the initially present species, A to zero. This equation is applicable for both slow and fast electron transfer. The diffusion coefficients (D) of the azocarbonyl compounds have been evaluated using equation (5) (Table 3) which are in a good agreement with those obtained in the case of DC polarography.

The deconvoluted current data (dI_1/dt) was obtained by the action of a semidifferentiation operator on the convoluted current, I_1 (Fig. 4). The shape of the deconvoluted current confirms $\text{EC}_{\text{irrev}}^8$ which is characterized by voltammograms of unequal heights for all electroactive reactant species under consideration. The reverse peak is much broader than the forward peak, as for example the data dI_1/dt recorded for the parent compound are shown in Fig. 4. The deconvolutions, dI_1/dt , for all the azocarbonyls under considerations are now well-displayed on either side of the half-wave potential. The values of half-peak width, $W_{1/2}$ (the width of the peak at half of its height) are shifted from the values obtained for one reversible electron transfer⁷.

Chronoamperometric and chronopotentiometric techniques: Fig. 5 shows a chronoamperogram for 3-

Fig. 4. Deconvoluted current for the first reduction wave of 1a at a sweep rate of 100 mV s^{-1} , $\text{pH} = 2.1$, $\text{concn.} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $\text{temp.} = 20^\circ$.

Fig. 5. Chronoamperogram for the reduction wave of 1a, pH = 2.1, concn. = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$, temp. = 20°.

arylazopentane-2,4-dione, under similar conditions to cyclic voltammetric experiments. The slow rise in current is due to a slight excess of damping. These results do not adhere to the Cottrell relationship as demonstrated by plots of $i\sqrt{t}$ versus t as shown in Fig. 6. The diffusion

Fig. 6. Plot of $i\sqrt{t}$ for the reduction wave of 1a, pH = 2.1, concn. = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$, temp. = 20°.

coefficients of the examined compounds are also evaluated using chronocoulometric analysis (Table 3). The straight-line relationships obtained by plotting charge/coulombs versus time/s or $\sqrt{t/s}$ for the azocarbonyl compounds allow us to evaluate the diffusion coefficient from the gradient of the charge versus the square-root of time¹² via

$$Q = \frac{2nFaC^* D^{1/2} t^{1/2}}{\pi^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 7. Chronopotentiogram for the reduction wave of 1a, pH = 2.1, concn. = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$, temp. = 20°.

where C is the concentration of the electroactive species and a the electrode area. The chronopotentiogram of the electroactive reactant species under consideration, in unstirred aqueous ethanolic buffer solutions under similar conditions to cyclic voltammetry technique, is shown in Fig. 7. At the onset of polarization, the potential decreased rapidly at first then gradually until there was an abrupt decrease to approximately the designated time (t_s), followed by a steady state potential. The diffusion coefficients for electroactive reactant species under consideration have been successfully evaluated from galvanostatic measurements using Sand equation¹⁴,

$$D^{1/2} = \frac{I_{lim}}{nFaD^{1/2}C} \quad (7)$$

where a is the electrode area. The values obtained agree well with values obtained from other related techniques, as shown in Table 3. The values of diffusion coefficients obtained from chronocoulometry and chronopotentiometry for all the azocarbonyl compounds compare well with those obtained from the plateau height of the I_1 convolution and limiting current of polarographic waves.

Electrochemical reaction mechanism : According to the above results, the electroreduction mechanism of electroactive reactant species can be explained as follows. The reduction step in acidic, neutral and alkaline solutions (pH ≤ 10) takes place for the azo group via the saturation by two electrons at E_1 and cleavage of the N–N bond by another two electrons at E_2 followed by $2e$ reduction of one of the carbonyl groups present in the molecule of the examined compounds. In view of fact that one of the carbonyl groups is in the enol form and charge

delocalization $[C-C-C]$, it can be concluded that one of

the two carbonyl groups⁴ is reduced. In highly alkaline solutions (pH >11), the N=N group is also reduced through 4e but no reduction of the carbonyl groups occurs. This could be a result of the hydration of one of the carbonyl groups since the other carbonyl group⁴ is in the enol form,

In solutions of pH ≤ 10,

i.e. 6 electrons are involved in the electrode reaction confirmed by CPC experiment (Table 1).

In solutions of pH > 11,

Structural effects : The plots of $E_{1/2}$ for the 3-arylazopentane-2,4-diones at two pH values (5 and 9) as a function of the Hammett substituent constant (σ_x) yield satisfactory linear relationship with positive slope ($\rho_{\pi, R}$) values varying between 0.10 and 0.13 V, indicating that the electroreduction process of the azo centres corresponds to nucleophilic attack in the potential-determining step, i.e. electron uptake¹⁵. The weak inductive effect of the substituent on the reaction centre is evidenced from the small values of $\rho_{\pi, R}$. Similar linear correlations are obtained with slopes ranging from 0.11 to 0.15 V, on plotting E_p values obtained from cyclic voltammetry at a sweep rate of 200 mV/s for arylazocarbonyl compounds as a function of the Hammett substituent constant σ_x at pH values 2.6, 7.65 and 11.6. This also confirms that the effect of substituents on the reaction centre under consideration is mainly inductive¹⁵.

Experimental

Arylazocarbonyl compound : The derivatives of aniline (10 mmol) was dissolved in HCl (20 mol in 25 ml distilled H₂O). The hydrochloride was diazotized below -5° with a solution of sodium nitrite (10 mmol in 30 ml distilled H₂O). The diazonium chloride was coupled with an alkaline solution of pentane-2,4-dione (10 mmol). The crude solid was crystallized from ethanol, dried in a vacuum desiccator over P₂O₅ and characterized by elemental analysis and spectral studies.

A 1:1 solution of NaOH (A.R., Vickers Laboratories Limited) was used for adjustment of pH of the buffer solution. Buffer solution consisting of phosphoric (AnalaR), acetic (B.D.H.) and boric (A.R.) acids covering the pH range 2-12, were prepared¹⁶. Ethanol (AnalaR) was used as such.

The polarograms were recorded using a Sargent-Welech 1004 polarograph. The cell used for the polarographic studies was of the simple type⁵ with a dropping mercury working electrode ($m = 1.559 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 4.5 \text{ s}$, mercury height 60 cm) and a saturated calomel electrode as a reference half-cell (Sargent-Welech). An EG & G 362 potentiostat and electrode assembly (model 303A) were used to generate the current flowing in the electrochemical cell. An EG & G electrode assembly with a hanging mercury drop electrode (area = $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$) as a working electrode, Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode and Pt wire as a counter electrode were used during the cyclic voltammetry measurement in aqueous media. A Princeton Applied Research Corporation (model 173) potentiostat for controlled potential electrolysis was used to control the potential of the working electrode.

References

1. R. F. HARMON, F. E. DUTTON, and H. P. WARREN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 627; D. C. SCHROEDER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1955, **55**, 181.
2. H. G. GRAD and P. P. SINGH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 612.
3. H. LUND, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, **17**, 2325; J. SERGRETARIO and P. ZUMAN, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1986, **214**, 137; P. N. GUPTA, A. RANIA, and V. K. BHAT, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1990, **2**, 73; J. BAREK, D. DREVINKOVA, J. ZIMA, and A. EOGGI, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1992, **57**, 2248; M. I. ISMAIL and M. ISKANDER, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1993, **58**, 1978; S. E. KHAN, K. JABARULLA, G. PARUTHIMAL, and T. VASUDERAN, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1992, **8**, 598; V. S. MURALIDHARAN, P. NAGARAJAN, and N. SULOCHANO, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1993, **2-3**, 9.
4. J. M. RODRIGUEZ-MELLADO, J. L. AVILA, and J. J. RUIZ, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1985, **63**, 891.
5. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 240.
6. D. ILKOVIC, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1934, **6**, 498.
7. A. J. BARD and L. R. FAULKNER, "Electrochemical Methods : Fundamentals and Applications", Wiley, New York, 1980.
8. J. LEDDY and A. J. BARD, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1985, **189**, 203.
9. R. S. LAWTON and A. M. YACYNCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1981, **53**, 1523.
10. J. C. IMBEAUX and J. M. SAVEANT, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1973, **44**, 169; K. B. OLDHAM, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1983, **145**, 9.
11. C. P. ANDRIEUX and J. M. SAVEANT, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1970, **26**, 147; J. M. SAVEANT and D. TESSIER, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1975, **65**, 57; A. NEUDECK and J. DITTRICH, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1989, **264**, 91.
12. F. G. COTTRELL, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, **42**, 385.
13. Y. I. MOHARRAM, Thesis, 1991, Tanta University, Egypt.
14. H. J. SAND, *Phil. Mag.*, 1902, **1**, 45.
15. L. P. HAMMETT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, **17**, 125.
16. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1952.